

Director's Message

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In the early morning hours of the first of August 2023, NOIRLab was subjected to a cyber incident that attempted to take down our systems. This was not the result of hacking by bored teenagers, but rather appears to have been the work of professionals who attack organizations around the world. Fortunately, these hackers had not fully done their homework — they struck at 2 a.m. on a Monday morning, apparently not realizing that observatories operate at night! Our crack IT team spotted the attack in real-time and disconnected Gemini North and all of Cerro Pachón and Cerro Tololo from the outside world just 40 minutes after the attack began. The hackers managed to encrypt many servers in Hawaii, but failed to have broader effects before being interrupted by our IT team's fast action. Crucially, we prevented our online backups from being affected. Nonetheless, it has been a long road back to “normal” operations. Following this incident, we have continued to enhance our security posture. Our internal network has undergone additional security enhancements to prevent intrusions and to limit any impact should another incident occur.

Unfortunately, cybercrime is on the rise, and other observatories, national laboratories, government agencies, universities, municipalities, nonprofits, and large corporations have been targeted. The frequency and sophistication of such attacks are increasing rapidly, and we are therefore in a constant race to keep our protections up to date. For example, all of us at NSF's NOIRLab participate in the “KnowBe4” security awareness training program.

NOIRLab management and our IT team learned a number of valuable lessons from this cyber incident. The first and foremost lesson is simple: be prepared, have a plan, and follow the plan. Our up-to-date Incident Response Plan was the key playbook in the hours and days following the attack. It greatly facilitated our ability to act swiftly, to work across all our sites, and to coordinate with NSF and AURA Corporate. Regular training and frequent full-scale incident response drills paid off when the real incident occurred.

A second lesson is that multi-factor authentication is a critical line of defense against attackers. It requires an extra step when logging in, but it is key to preventing unauthorized access to Lab networks.

Another key lesson that we will take away from this incident is that we must continue to focus on our communications with various stakeholders. We communicated closely with funding agencies and partners during the early days of our response efforts. However, in the future we will also focus on our communications with users of the mountain sites in Chile so they understand the state of the network and the timeline for restoration of services. Balancing caution with the need to keep people informed is a challenge, particularly when the security of our communications is in doubt.

The highest-level lesson from this experience, and the Kitt Peak fire, is that when we identify a high-impact risk we move with alacrity to mitigate it. We had a very sound plan and quickly implemented our IT security plan, but *we can always do better and move faster*. We have become very good at recovering from incidents, but *we must continue to focus on prevention*.

Part of what apparently made NOIRLab a tempting target for hackers is our transparent approach to operations and collaboration. Our mission as a national laboratory for astronomy and our commitments to our domestic and international partners require that we support many diverse users of our systems. Remote observing, rapid response to ToOs, citizen science programs, distributed collaborations, and close coordination between telescopes in the north and south are all best served with a network that is easy to access and easy to navigate. The power of this collaborative approach is documented in this edition of *The Mirror* through articles about Multi-Messenger Astrophysics, the *Cool Neighbors* citizen science project, the La Serena School for Data Science, and others. The story of the “Finch” luminous fast blue transient by Ashley Chrimes is a great example of multi-platform time-critical coordination.

Institutions with a scientific mission all face this challenge — science is best served by openness and collaboration — yet we must protect ourselves and our users from bad actors in the cyber domain. Our system was built over a number of decades to support scientific collaboration. In the past few months, we have optimized it from the ground up, enhancing our security while still supporting our mission. We hope that our experience can serve as a wake-up call for others so that they will not have to learn these lessons the hard way.